

Study of functionalized Au nanotubules membrane for chiral separation of penicillamine enantiomers

Lele Yang, Tengfei Ma, Peiyi Gao, Ling Yang, Qianqiong Guo and Shasheng Huang*

Life and Environmental Science College, Shanghai Normal University, Shanghai 200234, P. R. China

E-mail : sshuang@shnu.edu.cn

Manuscript received online 24 February 2015, accepted 25 March 2015

Abstract : In the present work, a method of chiral separation of penicillamine enantiomers based on L-cysteine coated Au nanotubules membrane was described. An electroless plating method was used to deposit Au onto the walls of pores of track-etched polycarbonate template membranes. The characteristics of the nanotubules were investigated by ultra-violet and visible spectroscopy (UV), infrared spectroscopy (IR) and other methods. The effects of the pore size of the nanotubules, the kinds and concentration of the modifiers and pH on the separation of penicillamine enantiomers were investigated. The coated nanotubules were verified by the separation of chiral penicillamine.

Keywords : Au nanotubules membrane, penicillamine enantiomers, chiral separation.

Introduction

Penicillamine, a kind of chiral materials, is extensively used in the medical field. D-Penicillamine and L-penicillamine are similar in the structure (Fig. 1) and physicochemical property, but they are different from medicinal chemistry and toxicity. D-Penicillamine is an important thiol compound. Clinically, D-penicillamine is used for the treatment of Wilson's disease, the prevention of infants' retina disease¹ and as an antidote in heavy-metal poisoning. In addition, it can also be used as the

Fig. 1. Molecular structures of D- (a), L- (b) and DL-penicillamines (c).

crucial intermediate of pharmaceutical synthesis². In contrast, L-penicillamine has been found to have considerable toxicity, as shown by several adverse reactions such as neuritis and osteomyelitis³. The separation of penicillamine enantiomers is of important significance.

Generally, penicillamine enantiomers were separated

using chromatography method⁴⁻⁷. Merino and his colleagues⁸ developed a high performance liquid chromatographic method for the resolution of penicillamine enantiomers based on a β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) column. Hidayat⁹ combined liquid chromatography and a tungsten electrode as an electrochemical detector to study the separation of penicillamine enantiomers. Gotti and his colleagues¹⁰ used 1,1'-[ethylenedibis-(sulfonyl)]bis-benzene as derivatization agent and β -cyclodextrin as a chiral selector to separate penicillamine enantiomers by capillary electrophoresis (CE). Yu and his colleagues¹¹ studied the discrimination of D-, L- and DL-penicillamine by terahertz time-domain spectroscopy (Thz-TDS). Lebrilla¹² reported that the ion/molecule reactions can be used to study the chiral recognition ability of chiral drugs (such as D-, L-penicillamine). The capillary electrophoresis, as a stronger method for the chiral separation, had been investigated for the separation of penicillamine enantiomers^{13,14}.

Nanotubule is an important way to study the separation and analysis of organic and biological molecules. In 1995, Martin¹⁵ used the template method to build Au nanotubules based on polymer template membrane. Many compounds have been separated by the Au nanotubules based on the sizes of molecules, ions and charge of the

compounds¹⁶⁻¹⁹. Huang reported the immunoreaction-based separation of antibodies using gold nanotubules membrane²⁰ and β -cyclodextrin modified silica nanochannel membrane for chiral separation²¹. However, there are few reports focusing on the chiral separation of penicillamine enantiomers using nanotubules. In this paper a high efficient separation technology for the separation of penicillamine enantiomers based on L-cysteine-coated Au nanotubules prepared by an electroless plating method to deposit Au onto the walls of pores within membranes was developed. The effects of the kinds and concentration of the modifiers and pH on the separation of penicillamine enantiomers were investigated. The coated membrane could be recycled used to separate penicillamine enantiomers and provided an alternative and good way for the separation of chiral drugs.

Results and discussion

Characterization of Au nanotubules membrane :

The Au nanotubules membranes (this membrane was denoted as Au-Mem) obtained at different plating time were characterized by field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM). With increasing the deposition time, the pore size of the nanotubules within the membrane decreased (Fig. 2). When the deposition time was 5 h, the diameter of the pore was about 20 nm.

Fig. 2. FESEM of Au nanotubules membrane. Depositing time : (a) 0 h; (b) 3 h; (c) 4 h; (d) 5 h.

Fig. 3 shows the infrared spectroscopy of Au-Mem and L-cysteine (L-cys) coated Au-Mem (this membrane was denoted as L-cys-Au-Mem). In the Fig. 3, according to the standard spectroscopy of L-cys, the peak at *ca.*

Fig. 3. Infrared spectra of Au nanochannel membrane modified by L-cys.

2570 cm^{-1} was considered to correspond to the vibration characteristic of thiol group. The characteristic absorption peak of vibration models of carboxyl was found at *ca.* 1733 cm^{-1} . These absorption peaks shown in Fig. 3 illustrated the successful modification of L-cys onto the walls of Au nanotubules.

AC impedance spectra of Au nanotubules membrane was shown in Fig. 4. The impedances of polycarbonate nanoporous membrane (PC-Mem) and Au-Mem were *ca.* $1000\ \Omega$ and $1350\ \Omega$, respectively. When the Au nanotubules were coated by L-cys, the impedance increased to *ca.* $1600\ \Omega$. The reason may be that the pore size of the nanotubules reduced with increasing the coating time of Au, resulting in an increase of the electron transfer

Fig. 4. AC impedance spectra of Au nanochannel membrane.

resistance through the membrane. For L-cys-Au-Mem, the electron transfer resistance of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-/3-}$ through the membrane further increased due to the modification of L-cys. The results showed the successful modification of L-cys.

Effect of chiral modifiers on the separation of enantiomers :

In order to build a chiral recognition layer at the surface of walls of Au pores, the selection of a suitable chiral modifier and the modification of Au nanotubes were crucial. As a thiol-containing amino acid, cysteine can react with Au at the surface of nanotubes by a strong binding affinity between Au and S atom. The effect of L-cys, D-cys and β -CD with SH group (SH- β -CD) chiral modifiers on the separation of penicillamine enantiomers was investigated. The transportation of 1 mM L-Pen and D-Pen with the same concentration as L-Pen through the Au-Mem with different chiral modifiers was shown in Fig. 5. In order to express the separation efficiency of the membrane for D-Pen and L-Pen one can

adopt α to express the separation efficiency :

$$\alpha = K_{\text{L-Pen}}/K_{\text{D-Pen}},$$

where $K_{\text{L-Pen}}$, $K_{\text{D-Pen}}$ are the transport rates of L-Pen and D-Pen through the membrane respectively.

From the curve a in Fig. 5, it can be seen that the transport rate of D-Pen and L-Pen through Au nanochannels was almost similar, indicating that penicillamine enantiomers could not be separated by Au nanotubes membrane because Au nanotubes membrane did not have chiral recognition layer, i.e. the separation efficiency of the Au-Mem without a chiral modifier was very poor. Using SH- β -CD as a chiral modifier, the separation efficiency was 1.201 (Fig. 5, curve b), and L-Pen passed more quickly through the membrane than D-Pen in this case. However, the improvement of separation efficiency of SH- β -CD-Au-Mem for L-Pen and D-Pen was not obvious, indicating that SH- β -CD did not show the selectivity for L-Pen and D-Pen. When L-cys or D-cys was coated onto the Au-nanotubes, the difference of transport rates

Fig. 5. Separation efficiency of penicillamine enantiomers through the Au-Mem (a), SH- β -CD-Au-Mem (b), D-cys-Au-Mem (c) and L-cys-Au-Mem (d) (Depositing time : 4 h).

of L-Pen and D-Pen through D-cys-Au-Mem or L-cys-Au-Mem obviously increased (Fig. 5c, 5d). The reason may be that L/D-cys, as a chiral modifier, showed different forces for L-Pen and D-Pen. L-Pen was recognized easily by the chiral recognition site of L/D-cys and transported through the L/D-cys-Au-Mem more easily than D-Pen. However, the transportation rate of Pen was slower when D-cys was used as the chiral modifier due to the different structures of L/D cysteine, we chose L-cys as the chiral modifier for further research.

Au nanoparticles modified by L-cys showed the selective adsorption to enantiomers²². The transport rate of analyte through nanotubules membrane was affected by the interaction between the analytes and the chiral modifiers. Song *et al.*²³ used a fluorescent sensor to analyze D- and L-cysteine in mixtures. They found that cysteine could form a dimer with stable structure, cysteine-cysteine. The heterochiral (L- and D-cysteine) interaction leads to more notable fluorescence resonance energy transfer efficiencies as compared with homochiral (L-L or D-D-cysteine) interaction. In order to verify whether Song's idea can be taken in our separation system reported here, we investigated the separation of penicillamine enantiomers using Au-Mem coated with L-Pen (this membrane was denoted as L-Pen-Au-Mem) and repeated this experiment several times. The results showed that the transport rate of L-Pen through L-Pen-Au-Mem was larger than that of D-Pen (Fig. 6). In other words, L-Pen was easily recognized by L-Pen coated in the nanotubules of Au-Mem, which was contrary to Song's idea. Fig. 7 shows

Fig. 6. Separation efficiency of penicillamine enantiomers through the L-Pen-Au-Mem (Depositing time : 4 h).

the separation principle diagram using L-cys-Au-Mem to separate penicillamine enantiomers.

The effect of the concentration of the chiral modifiers in the modification solution on penicillamine enantiomers separation was shown in Fig. 8. When the concentration of L-cys was lower than 0.5 mM, the separation efficiency of penicillamine enantiomers was poor. When the concentration of L-cys was too high, the recognition of the site was reduced and the separation effect was not good either. The separation effect was the best when the concentration of L-cys was 1 mM.

Effect of the pore size on penicillamine enantiomers separation :

The separation of enantiomers was greatly influenced

Fig. 7. The separation principle diagram.

Fig. 8. Effect of the concentration of L-cys on the penicillamine enantiomers separation.

by Au nanotubules pore size. Generally, when an electroless plating method was used to deposit Au on the nanotubules, the pore size of the Au nanotubules decreased with increasing the deposition time. The separation efficiency of penicillamine enantiomers through functionalized Au nanotubules obtained at different deposition time was examined (Fig. 9). When the deposition time was 5 h, the

Fig. 9. Effect of the pore size on the separation of penicillamine enantiomers.

best separation efficiency can be obtained. The deposition time was controlled at 5 h in the following experiments.

Effect of pH on separation of penicillamine enantiomers :

The impact of pH value of PBS solution on the separa-

tion of penicillamine enantiomers was investigated (Fig. 10). From the Fig. 10, in a pH 6.0 PBS solution, a largest separation efficiency was obtained (We can't find the data on the isoelectric point of penicillamine. However, the structure of penicillamine is similar to D-3-SH valine, the isoelectric point of valine is 5.97, we estimate that the isoelectric point of penicillamine is similar to that of valine). The separation efficiency decreased whether pH of the buffer solution is less than or greater than the isoelectric point of the penicillamine.

Fig. 10. Effect of pH on penicillamine enantiomers separation.

A preliminary application of nanotubules membrane, separation of chiral drugs and repeated utilization of the membrane :

To separate enantiomers from a mixture containing D-Pen and L-Pen, 50 nm polycarbonate film deposited Au for 5 h was used to investigate the transportation characteristics of penicillamine enantiomers through the Au nanochannels membrane and L-cys functionalized Au nanochannels membrane, respectively. Under the optimal experimental conditions, the amounts of D-Pen and L-Pen transported through Au nanochannels membranes was determined using a polarimeter. Under the optimal conditions, when the deposition was 5 h and the modifier was 1 mM L-cys in a pH 6.0 PBS solution, the separation efficiency of functionalized Au nanotubules membrane for the penicillamine enantiomers was 4.295 (Fig. S1).

To improve the efficiency of the experiments, one

Fig. S1. Migration figure of 10^{-3} M penicillamine enantiomers by functional Au nanochannels when the deposition was 5 h and the modifier was 1 mM L-cys in a pH 6.0 PBS solution (the party point means L-Pen, the dot means D-Pen).

piece of the membranes was reused for 5 times for the separation of analytes. The results showed that the similar results for chiral separation of penicillamine enantiomers were obtained (Fig. 11) as long as the membrane was not broken, indicating that this method had good reproducibility.

Fig. 11. Repeated utilization times of the membrane.

Experimental

Materials :

The electrochemical measurements were carried out at the electrochemical workstation (CHI 760C, Shanghai Chenhua). The concentrations of L-penicillamine and D-

penicillamine in the permeating cell were detected by a polarimeter (Autopol IV/IV, USA). The field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, S4800, HITACHI) and Infrared Spectroscopy (Thermo Nicolet iS10) were used to characterize the nanotubules membrane.

Polycarbonate nanoporous filtration membranes with pore diameters of 50 nm, thickness of 6 μ m, and pore densities of 6×10^8 pores/cm² (PCTM, Whatman Company, England) were used to prepare Au nanochannels. D-Penicillamine (D-Pen) and L-penicillamine (L-Pen) were obtained from Beijing Lark Technology Co., Ltd. SH- β -cyclodextrin (SH- β -CD) and L-cysteine (L-cys) were purchased from Sigma.

All reagents used in the experiments were of analytical grade. Milli-Q 18.2 M Ω water was used throughout all experiments.

Methods :

Preparation and modification of nanotubules membrane :

The Au nanotubules were prepared by depositing Au onto the inner walls of nanopore of the polycarbonate membrane using an electroless plating method^{15,24}. The template membrane was immersed into methanol solution and ultrasonically vibrated for 5 min and then immersed in SnCl₂ solution and shaken constantly and slightly for 45 min. The membrane was immersed in Ag(NH₃)₂⁺ solution under protecting with N₂ gas for 10 min prior to wash with methanol and water three times, respectively. After the membrane was placed in the gold-plating bath at 4 °C (pH = 10.0) for 5 h, the membrane was washed three times with water and immersed into 25% HNO₃ for 12 h to remove the impurities adsorbed on the surface of the membrane. According to the report²⁵, thiol chemisorption was accomplished by immersion of the Au nanotubules membrane into a 1 mM solution of L-cys, SH- β -CD or L-Pen for 24 h, respectively. In the process of chemisorption, continuous ventilation was kept under the protection of N₂ gas. The membrane was then dried in the air. In this paper, PC-Mem, Au-Mem, L-cys-Au-Mem and SH- β -CD-Au-Mem were used to denote the naked polycarbonate nanoporous filtration membrane, polycarbonate nanoporous filtration membrane covered

Fig. S2. Migration figure of L-Pen by L-cys-Au-Mem.

with gold, Au-nanotubule membrane coated with L-cys and Au-nanotubule membrane coated with SH- β -CD, respectively.

Ac impedance spectroscopy of the nanotubes membrane :

Two Pt wires, where one was used as the working electrode and another as auxiliary electrode, were inserted into the feed cell of the separation apparatus mounted with nanotubes film and a saturated calomel electrode used as reference electrode was inserted in the permeate cell. The impedance measurements were made in 0.1 M KNO₃ solution containing 1 mM K₃[Fe(CN)₆]/K₄[Fe(CN)₆] (1 : 1). The frequency varied from 0.01 Hz to 10 KHz.

Separation and determination of penicillamine enantiomers :

The apparatus used for the separation of penicillamine enantiomers based on nanotubes membrane was the same as that described before²⁶. The membrane was mounted between two halves of a U-tube permeate cell. 1 mM PBS solution contained 1 mM penicillamine enantiomers was put into the feed cell while 1 mM PBS solution of the same volume was put into the permeate cell to keep the same height of liquid surface in both cells. In other words, the equal liquid level between feed cell and permeate cell was maintained during the experiment. The permeate half-cell was sampled, and the polarimeter was used to determine the flux of the analytes transported periodically.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Project of the National Science Foundation of People's Republic of China (21275100), Shanghai Leading Academic Discipline Project (S30406) and Key Laboratory of Resource Chemistry of Ministry of Education.

References

1. D. L. Phelps and L. Lakatos, *Cochrane. Database. Syst. Rev.*, 2001, **1**, CD001073.
2. J. C. Sheehun and K. H. Henery-Lock, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **79**, 1262.
3. W. F. Kean, C. J. L. Lock and H. E. Howard-Lock, *Lancet.*, 1991, **338**, 1565.
4. E. Busker, K. Giinther and J. Martens, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1985, **350**, 179.
5. W. A. König, K. Ernst and E. Steinbach, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1984, **301**, 129.
6. K. Nakashima, T. Ishimarn, N. Kuroda and S. Akiyama, *Biomed. Chromatogr.*, 1995, **9**, 90.
7. F. Nachtmann, *J. Pharm.*, 1980, **4**, 337.
8. I. M. Merino, E. B. González and A. Sanz-Medel, *Microchim. Acta*, 1992, **107**, 73.
9. A. Hidayat and D. B. Hibbert, *J. Chromatogr. (B)*, 1997, **693**, 139.
10. R. Gotti and R. Pomponio, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 1999, **844**, 361.
11. X. H. Yu, T. Ji, H. W. Zhao, Z. Y. Zhang, M. Ge, W. W. Wang and H. Xu, *J. Acta Phys. Chim. Sin.*, 2006, **22**, 1159.
12. G. Grigorean, X. Cong and C. B. Lebrilla, *Int. J. Mass. Spectrom.*, 2004, **234**, 71.
13. M. He, S. Zhao and J. Chen, *Chin. J. Anal. Chem.*, 2006, **34**, 655.
14. Z. X. Zheng, J. M. Lin, F. Qu and T. Hobo, *Electrophoresis*, 2003, **24**, 4221.
15. K. B. Jirage, J. C. Hulteen and C. R. Martin, *Science*, 1997, **278**, 655.
16. V. P. Menon and C. R. Martin, *Anal. Chem.*, 1995, **67**, 1920.
17. Z. Hou, N. L. Abbott and P. Stroeve, *Langmuir*, 2000, **16**, 2401.
18. T. C. Kuo, L. A. Sloan, J. V. Sweedler and P. W. Bohn, *Langmuir*, 2001, **17**, 6298.
19. S. B. Lee and C. R. Martin, *Anal. Chem.*, 2001, **73**, 768.
20. S. S. Huang, C. Sheng, Z. F. Yin, J. Shen, R. N. Li and B. Peng, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 2007, **305**, 257.

21. Y. Liu, P. Li, L. Xie, D. Y. Fan and S. S. Huang, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 2014, **453**, 12.
22. L. Song, M. R. Hobaugh and C. Shustak, *Science*, 1996, **274(5294)**, 1859.
23. L. Song, S. F. Wang, N. A. Kotov and Y. S. Xia, *Anal. Chem.*, 2012, **84**, 7330.
24. S. S. Huang and Y. F. Yin, *Anal. Sci.*, 2006, **22**, 1005.
25. S. Biggs, P. Mulvaney and C. F. Zukoski, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 9150.
26. S. S. Huang, G. M. Yu and X. X. He, *Chinese Science Bulletin*, 2004, **49**, 1368.